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Research Article

Computational, Molecular Docking, ADME/T And AIM Investigations Of 7-(4-Nitrophenyl) Benzo [6,7] Chromeno[3,2-E] Pyrido[1,2-A] Pyrimidin-6(7H)-One

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ABSTRACT

In the present research work, 7-(4-nitrophenyl) benzo [6,7] chromeno [3,2-e] pyrido [1,2-a] pyrimidin-6(7H)-one was synthesized by multicomponent reaction (MCR) with β -naphthol and 4-nitrobenzaldehyde. The synthesized product was obtained in a good yield, and its structures was established based on UV-Vis, FT-IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and HRMS analysis. To validate the experimental findings, in-silico studies of one synthesized compound 6 were done with the help of density functional theory (DFT) at B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level. Ultra-violet, IR, molecular electrostatic potential, NLO, NBO, thermodynamic parameter, reactivity descriptor, and AIM Reduced density gradient analysis were performed to better understand the electronic properties, and reactivity. The synthesized pyridopyrimidine compounds had an antimicrobial impact, in some cases much more potent than the reference medication. The molecular docking studies revealed an excellent affinity for the active sites of the matching gene regulation-inhibitor complex (7DKP) protein. Additionally, the evaluation of ADMET parameters indicated good pharmacokinetic properties of all the investigated compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Pyrimidines represent a versatility in *N*-heterocyclic compounds and displayed a verity of advantages such as low toxicity, good solubility, simple synthetic methods and low cost [1]. From past decayed pyrimidine derivatives have received

considerable attention in biological and pharmacological applications, such as anticancer [2], antitumor [3], antiproliferative [4], anti-HIV [5], anti-inflammatory [6], antioxidant, anticonvulsant [7], antihypertensive [8], anti-Alzheimer's [9], antitubercular [10], anticoagulant [11], antiviral [12], antifungal [13], antimicrobial

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[14], and antimalarial [15]. Pyrimidines have fluorescence sensors, optical chemosensors, photosensitizers, photocatalysis as well as latent fingerprint applications because of its photophysical properties (Fig.1) [16]. In current scenario Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) have recently gained considerable economic and ecological interest as they address basic principles of synthetic efficiency and reaction design. Multi-component reactions have been endorsed to be a very exquisite and expeditious way to access complex structures in a single synthetic operation from simple building blocks, featuring high atom economy and high selectivity [17]. As a one-pot reaction, MCRs generally afford good yields, and they entirely differ from two-component reactions in several facet [18,19]. On the other hand, conceptual DFT is a branch of Density Functional Theory that has been assembled and enforced in distinct branches of chemistry [20]. Using computational approaches to explore various aspects of a molecule offers a significant time and financial advantage. Thus, atomic charges, molecular shape, dipole moment, reactive descriptors, NBO, etc are all calculated using DFT

[21]. Some geometrical and structural parameters were computed and calculated for any pyridopyrimidine derivatives [22], but no work was published for the theoretical calculation about heteroannulated 2H-pyrido[1,2-a] pyrimidin-2-one. On the basis of mathematical and statistical relationships pathways are decisive for anticipating the biological effects of chemical stuffs [23]. The ongoing work is directed to utilize multi component reactions of 2H-pyrido[1,2-a] pyrimidin-2-one (**1**) for building a new series of 2H-pyrido[1,2-a] pyrimidin-2-one and their related compounds, in addition to evaluate their antimicrobial activity [24]. Further, DFT at the B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level was used to correlate the theoretical data from the DFT calculations with the experimental results of synthesized 7-(4-nitrophenyl)benzo[6,7]chromeno[3,2e]pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-6(7H)-one using Gaussian 09 programme. Moreover, Molecular docking, AIM and ADME, experimentally and theoretically based on DFT as well as predicting their pharmacokinetics and drug-likeness properties using efficient in silico methods [25].

Fig. 1 Biologically active Pyridopyrimidines derivatives

2. Experimental

Merck and Sigma Aldrich branded chemicals were purchased from the local seller for the completion of current research work. The synthesized compound was conveniently dissolved in chloroform (CHCl₃) and this solution led to initial

confirmation of synthesis by thin layer chromatography. Ethyl acetate and n-hexane in wavering proportion collectively made the mobile phase while coated silica on aluminum plate incorporated the stationary phase and was observed under ultraviolet light of 254 nm wavelength. The FT-IR characterization was performed by KBr

pellet method in Jasco FTIR spectrometer was used for the confirmation of functional groups present in different compounds. The further characterization was performed by ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR using Bruker spectrometers, operated at 600 and 150 MHz, respectively. The reference used was tetramethylsilane (TMS) while chloroform was used as solvent. Furthermore, the confirmation was also substantiated by EI-MS spectra using Jasco-320-A spectrophotometer.

2.1 Synthesis of 7-(4-nitrophenyl) benzo[6,7]chromeno[3,2-e]pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-6(7H)-one:

The synthesis of 2H-

pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidine-2,4(3H)-dione (3), m.p. 296–298 °C by the reported method. The ascertained analytical and spectral data were found in entire obedience with the literature values. The reaction of p-nitrobenzaldehyde 5 (1.0 mmol), 2-naphthol (4) (1.0 mmol), DMSO (1-2 drops) and 2H-pyrido[1,2-a] pyrimidine-2,4(3H)-dione (3) (1.2 mmol) in refluxing toluene for about 24-27 hrs was performed as a model reaction in the presence of catalyst P_2O_5 (20 mol). The desired product resulted in good yields. To explore the generality of the reaction, we extended our study using P_2O_5 (20 mol %) as catalyst in toluene solvent [26] (Scheme 1.).

Scheme. 1 Synthetic Route Of 7-(4-Nitrophenyl) Benzo [6,7] Chromeno[3,2-E]Pyrido[1,2-A]Pyrimidin-6(7H)-One

2.3. Computational details

The Gaussian 09 software package was used for all DFT computations and the Gauss View 5.0.8 tool was used to frame-up the outputting. At the B3LYP (Becke's three parameter hybrid model adopting the Lee-Yang Parr correlation functional)

level of DFT with 6-311G(d,p) basis set [27], quantum chemical calculations such as optimized geometries and corresponding molecule orbitals (MOs) energies, molecular electrostatic potential (MEP), and Fukui functions were accomplished. ^1H NMR chemical shifts were performed with the Gauge-Including Atomic Orbital (GIAO)

approach by using the aforesaid basis theory level and compared with the experimental ^1H NMR chemical shift values. Subtracting the calculated absolute chemical shielding of TMS, the ^1H NMR chemical shifts were transferred into the TMS scale B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) [28]. The molecular electronic dipole moment, polarizability, and the first hyper-polarizability were all described using the same level of the DFT.

2.4. ADME analysis

Pharmacokinetics and physicochemical features of formed stuffs were approximated using computational analysis. ADME is enforced for the development of drugs to be successful. This tool offers a wide range of factors, including drug-likeness rules, lipophilicity, molar refractivity, molecular weight, number of rotatable bonds, hydrogen bond acceptor, hydrogen bond donor, and medicinal chemistry access [29].

3.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Characterization of the synthesized compound (6)

Dark brown solid; m.p.: 263-265 °C; Yield: ~67%; R_f : 0.57; [Hexane: Ethyl acetate] (9.0:1.0 v/v) as mobile phase; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3062 (=CH stretching); 2922 (-CH stretching), 1795 (C=O stretching), 1595 (-C=C- stretching), 1514 (-NO₂ stretching); 1340 (-C-N stretching); 1107 (-C-O stretching), ^1H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ (ppm,): 8.20-8.17 (d, 3H), 7.91-7.89 (d, 1H), 7.75-7.73 (d,

2H), 7.60-7.43 (m, 6H), 7.39-6.32 (d, 1H), 7.16-6.50 (d, 1H), 4.13 (s, 1H), ^{13}C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 67.00, 114.59, 116.89, 120.86, 122.70, 123.41, 126.02, 127.64, 127.80, 127.89, 128.43, 129.74, 129.89, 131.27, 145.11, 147.59, 150.85, 166.64; ESI-MS: m/z 422.7 [M+1]⁺, Calculated m/z=421, molecular formula: C₂₅H₁₅N₃O₄.

3.2. Theoretical studies

3.2.1 ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts were calculated with Gauge Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) approach using DFT method and B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) as basis sets [30]. The experimental and theoretical values of ^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts of the studied compound are given in Table 1. The correlation graph between the experimental and calculated chemical shifts for ^1H and ^{13}C NMR are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. S1, S2, S3 displayed ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and mass spectra respectively. The correlation graph follows the linear equation, $y = 0.501x + 61.36$ using HF for ^1H NMR and $y = 0.696x + 2.384$ for ^{13}C NMR where 'y' is the ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR experimental chemical shift and 'x' is the calculated ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR chemical shift (in ppm). The correlation values ($R^2 = 0.624$ using B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)) for ^1H NMR and ($R^2 = 0.727$ using B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)) for ^{13}C NMR shows that the correlations between experimental and the calculated chemical shifts are very good.

Table 1. Experimental and calculated ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (ppm) of the molecule using B3LYP/6-311G(D, P).

Carbon atom	Calculated ^{13}C NMR chemical Shift	Experimental ^{13}C NMR chemical shift	Hydrogen atom	Calculated ^1H NMR chemical shift	Experimental ^1H NMR chemical shift
C1	141.5535	145.11	H33	7.2676	7.16
C2	107.2045	131.27	H34	6.2774	6.5
C3	127.8111	129.89	H35	8.0269	7.91
C5	157.1279	147.59	H36	6.6343	7.36

C6	118.7769	129.74	H37	4.0843	4.13
C7	146.9308	128.43	H38	7.2291	7.86
C8	94.7065	127.89	H39	6.7124	7.75
C9	177.7245	150.85	H40	7.0925	7.73
C12	143.1317	127.8	H41	6.9495	7.6
C13	119.0723	127.64	H42	6.7899	7.51
C14	27.903	67	H43	6.9163	7.53
C15	113.9749	126.02	H42	7.9545	7.47
C16	131.5466	125.04	H45	8.377	7.43
C17	129.4353	124.28	H46	8.2197	7.39
C18	133.1936	123.99	H47	6.1813	7.34
C20	129.531	123.41			
C21	127.5112	122.7			
C22	126.2836	121.67			
C23	190.4958	166			
C24	134.8868	120.86			
C25	135.3075	119.58			
C26	139.8524	117.85			
C27	134.7439	116.89			
C28	126.0938	114.59			

Fig. 2 Correlation graph between experimental and calculated ¹³CNMR chemical shifts and between experimental and calculated ¹HNMR chemical shifts using B3LYP/6-311G (D, P).

3.2.2 UV-Visible absorption spectroscopy

The UV-Visible spectrum of compound has been studied by TD-DFT method using B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) basis sets and solvent effect has been

taken into consideration by implementing Integral Equation Formalism Polarizable Continuum Model (IEFPCM). The vertical excitation energies, oscillator strengths (f), percentage contribution of probable transitions and

corresponding absorption wavelengths along with simulated UV data have been tabulated in **Table 2** and compared with experimental results [31]. The intense electronic transitions at 334, 246 and 189 nm with oscillator strengths $f = 0.7965$, 0.2392 and 1.1334 in CHCl_3 are anticipated, showing an agreement with the measured experimental data ($\lambda_{\text{exp.}} = 326, 260$ and 205 nm in CHCl_3) as shown in **Fig. 3**. Electronic transitions from HOMO to LUMO, HOMO-1 to LUMO+1, HOMO-1 to

LUMO+5, HOMO-2 to LUMO+2, HOMO-2 to LUMO+3 and HOMO-2 to LUMO+4 with 34%, 48%, 40%, 36%, 28% and 42% contributions respectively. The corresponding theoretical peak in the TD-DFT UV spectrum is at 226nm. These transitions are due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. Molecular orbitals HOMO-LUMO, (HOMO-1)-LUMO, (HOMO-1)-(LUMO+1) and (HOMO-1)-(LUMO+3) of the compound are shown in Fig 4.

S. No.	Major contributing Molecular orbitals	E (eV)	Calculated (λ_{max})	Oscillatory strength (f)	Assignment	Observed (λ_{max})
1	H→L (34%)	3.71	334	0.7965	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	326
2	H-1→L+1 (48%)	5.03	246	0.2392	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	
3	H-1→L+5 (40%)	5.97	207	0.4003	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	260
4	H-2→L+2 (30%)	6.36	194	1.5461	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
5	H-2→L+5 (28%)	6.54	189	1.1334	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	205
6	H-2→L+3 (34%)	6.92	179	1.2907	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	

Fig. 3 Experimental and Theoretical UV spectrum of the molecule

Fig. 4 Homo-Lumo Transitions of The Molecule

3.2.3 Vibrational Assignment

The vibrational analysis of molecule shows the presence of 47 atoms which belong to C1 point group possessing 138 normal modes of vibrations. Representative experimental FT-IR bands together with calculated wave numbers (scaled) and their assignments are given in Table 3. The value of correlation coefficient ($R^2=0.998$ using DFT) showed an excellent correlation between experimental and calculated wave numbers. Fig. 5 represents the correlation graph and FT-IR spectra (experimental and calculated) are shown in Fig. 6. The hetero aromatic organic compounds and their derivatives are structurally very close to benzene and commonly exhibit multiple weak bands in the region $3100-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is the characteristic region for the identification of C-H stretching vibrations and these vibrations are not found to be affected due to the nature and position of the

substituents [32]. In the present work, the hydrogen atoms around the pyridopyrimidine ring of molecule give rise three C-H stretching mode at 3062 cm^{-1} experimentally. The calculated frequencies for these vibrations were obtained in the range of 2994 cm^{-1} using the B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) methods. A strong band at 1795 cm^{-1} in FT-IR spectrum corresponds to -C=O stretching vibrations. The wave number calculated at 1715 cm^{-1} for B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level assigned to the -C=O stretching vibration in the molecule. The stretching mode of the -C-N group is found to be at 1340 cm^{-1} which shows good agreement with the experimental value i.e. 1343 cm^{-1} . The -C-O stretching vibrations are generally observed at around $1150-1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the experimental spectrum, the band observed at 1107 cm^{-1} has been assigned for -C-O stretching vibration and is in good agreement with the calculated value at 1062 cm^{-1} .

Table 3. Experimental FT-IR and calculated vibrational frequencies in cm^{-1} for molecule using B3LYP/6-311G(D,P).		
Experimental (cm^{-1})	Calculated wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Vibrational assignment
3062	2994.722	=CH stretching
2922	2815.716	-C-H stretching
1795	1715.555	C=O stretching
1595	1503.65	-C=C- stretching
1514	1440.756	-NO ₂ stretching
1340	1343.996	-C-N stretching
1107	1062.425	-C-O stretching

Fig. 5 Correlation graph between experimental and calculated wave numbers.

Fig. 6 Experimental and theoretical FT-IR spectra the molecule molecule

3.2.4 Molecular electrostatic potential

MESP provides a visual method to understand the relative polarity of a molecule and used to identify

the sites for hydrogen bonding interactions [33]. MESP of the molecule are shown in Fig. 7. The range of total electron density lies from -2.28×10^{-2} to $+2.28 \times 10^{-2}$ electrons per cubic Bohr.

Fig. 7 3D plot of the molecular electrostatic potential of molecule

3.2.5 Natural bond orbital analysis

The Natural Bond Analysis (NBO) [34] has been performed using Gaussian09 package at the B3LYP/6-311G(d,p). It explains charge transfer or conjugative interactions in molecular systems, intra and intermolecular bonding and interaction among bonds. The corresponding results are presented in **Table 4**.

NBO Analysis Showed That Intramolecular Charge Transfer Is:

- ❖ From $n(\text{C5-N10})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C1-C6})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 42.69 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $\pi(\text{C2-C3})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C1-C6})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 26.92 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $n(\text{C5-N10})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C1-C6})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 11.62 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $n(\text{C9-O29})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C7-C8})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 35.78 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $\pi(\text{C12-C15})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C13-C18})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 34.23 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $\pi(\text{C13-C18})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C12-C15})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 35.97 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $\pi(\text{C19-C20})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C21-C22})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 31.18 kJ/mol.
- ❖ From $\pi(\text{C21-C22})$ to $\pi^*(\text{C19-C20})$ antibonding orbitals with stabilization energy of 62.73 kJ/mol.
- ❖ Electron donated from LP(1) of N10 to $\pi^*(\text{C13-C18})$ leads to the stabilization energy of 52.92 kJ/mol.

- ❖ Electron donated from LP(1) of N4 to π^* (C21-C22) leads to the stabilization energy of 62.73 kJ/mol.

Table 4. Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix in NBO basis of the molecule.

Donor	Type	ED/e	Acceptor(j)	Type	ED/e	E(2)a	(Ej-Ei)b	Fij(c)
C1 - C6	n	1.97	C5 - N10	π^*	0.334	42.69	0.5	0.135
C1 - H33	σ	1.85	C2 - C3	σ^*	0.042	5.36	1.61	0.083
C1 - H33	σ	1.97	C5 - C6	σ^*	0.037	8.47	1.44	0.099
C2 - C3	n	1.97	N4 - C7	π^*	0.288	6.03	1.63	0.089
C2 - C3	π	1.96	C1 - C6	π^*	0.024	26.92	0.6	0.114
C2 - H34	n	1.98	C3 - N4	σ^*	0.322	9.83	1.33	0.102
C3 - H35	σ	1.97	C1 - C2	σ^*	0.326	7.03	1.49	0.091
C3 - H35	n	1.97	N4 - C5	π^*	0.288	8.11	1.36	0.095
C5 - C6	n	1.96	N4 - C7	π^*	0.326	6.72	1.54	0.091
C5 - C6	n	1.95	C9 - N10	π^*	0.371	7.36	1.63	0.098
C5 - N10	n	1.98	C1 - C6	π^*	0.023	11.62	0.64	0.078
C6 - H36	n	1.98	N4 - C5	π^*	0.054	7.99	1.31	0.092
C7 - C8	n	1.97	C9 - O29	π^*	0.254	35.78	0.58	0.134
C7 - C8	π	1.97	C14 - C23	π^*	0.067	5.22	0.99	0.066
C8 - C9	π	1.97	C7 - O11	π^*	0.037	9.18	1.46	0.103
C8 - C14	π	1.96	C23-C22	π^*	0.288	5.87	0.77	0.075
C8 - C14	n	1.96	N4 - C7	π^*	0.024	7.54	1.47	0.094
C9 - N10	n	1.98	C5 - C6	π^*	0.322	5.56	1.77	0.089
C9 - O29	n	1.98	C5 - C11	π^*	0.371	5.36	0.63	0.056
C9 - O29	n	1.98	C7 - C8	π^*	0.023	6.67	0.66	0.062
C12 - C13	π	1.97	C12 - C15	π^*	0.054	5.19	1.8	0.087
C12 - C15	π	1.97	C12 - C13	π^*	0.084	5.25	1.74	0.086
C12 - C15	π	1.97	C13 - C18	π^*	0.371	34.23	0.55	0.123
C13 - C18	n	1.75	O11 - C12	π^*	0.581	6.51	1.47	0.087
C13 - C18	n	1.75	LP(1) C17	π^*	0.033	52.92	0.3	0.143
C13 - C18	π	1.96	C12 - C15	π^*	0.024	35.97	0.54	0.125
C14 - H37	π	1.96	C23 - C28	π^*	0.018	7.26	1.43	0.091
C15 - C16	π	1.97	O11 - C12	π^*	0.012	7.39	1.42	0.091
C15 - H38	σ	1.97	C12 - C13	π^*	0.033	8.76	1.48	0.102
C17 - C18	π	1.98	C13 - C14	π^*	0.021	6.64	1.52	0.09
C19 - C20	π	1.97	C15 - C16	π^*	0.0203	5.42	1.72	0.086
C19 - C20	n	1.97	C21 - C22	π^*	0.014	31.18	0.54	0.117
C20 - H41	σ	1.97	C21 - C22	π^*	0.0122	5.85	1.57	0.086
C21 - C22	n	1.97	C17 - C18	π^*	0.203	5.52	1.72	0.087
C21 - C22	n	1.97	LP(1) C17	π^*	0.03	62.73	0.26	0.147
C21 - C22	π	1.97	C19 - C20	π^*	0.035	31.89	0.54	0.118

C22 - H43	σ	1.68	C20 - C21	π^*	0.015	6.86	1.49	0.09
C24 - H44	σ	1.85	C23 - C28	π^*	0.0175	8.07	1.47	0.097
C27 - C28	n	1.75	C14 - C23	π^*	0.27	5.37	1.58	0.082

$E(2)^a$ means energy of hyperconjugative interactions (stabilization energy in Kcal/mol) ($E_j - E_i$)^b Energy difference between donor and acceptor i and j NBO orbitals in a.u. $F_{ij}^{(c)}$ is the Fock matrix elements between i and j NBO orbitals in a.u.

3.2.6 Nonlinear optical analysis

The first hyperpolarizability of the studied compound was computed using the B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) basis set and the total dipole moment μ , the average polarizability α_{tot} and the first hyperpolarizability β_{tot} were calculated [35].

Since the values of the polarizabilities α and the hyperpolarizability of Gaussian output are reported in atomic mass units (a.u.), the calculated values have been converted into electrostatic units (esu) (α : 1 a.u = 0.1482×10^{-24} esu; β : 1 a.u. = $0.0086393 \times 10^{-30}$ esu). The results of electronic dipole moment μ_i ($i = x, y, z$), polarizability α_{ij} and first order hyperpolarizability β_{ijk} are presented in Table 5. The calculated dipole moment, polarizability α_{tot} and first hyper polarizability for the title compound are equal to 10.9928 D, 46.35×10^{-24} esu and 50.7636×10^{-30} esu respectively for DFT level.

Table 5. Dipole Moment μ , Polarizability α_{tot} ($\times 10^{-24}$ esu) and first order static hyperpolarizability β_{tot} (10^{-30} esu) data of the molecule			
Dipole moment	B3LYP/6-311G(D,P)	Hyperpolarisability	B3LYP/6-311G(D,P)
μ_x	-7.6106	β_{xxx}	-16.1036
μ_y	-2.6182	β_{xxy}	-11.2294
μ_z	7.4877	β_{xyy}	-14.1538
μ	10.9928	β_{yyy}	-30.9518
Polarizability			
α_{xx}	53.48523	β_{xxz}	4.07978
α_{xy}	66.64984	β_{xyz}	6.154845
α_{yy}	55.82694	β_{yyz}	7.121703
α_{xz}	50.95086	β_{xzz}	3.702389
α_{yz}	4.678215	β_{yzz}	0.090047
α_{zz}	29.76597	β_{zzz}	-1.19513
(α)	46.35938	β_{total} (esu)	50.7636

3.2.7 Thermodynamic Properties

Thermodynamic parameter of title compound, including zero-point vibrational energy, rotational temperatures, rotational constants, energies at standard temperature (298.15 K) were obtained at B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) basis set and are presented

Table 6 [36]. Many useful information's can be generated from these thermodynamic data and can be used to compute other thermodynamic energies, according to the relationships of thermodynamic functions and estimate directions of chemical reactions according to the second law of thermodynamics in thermo chemical field. All

thermodynamic calculations were done in gas phase and they could not be used in solution.

Parameters	B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)
Zero-point vibrational energy (Kcal/mol)	245.999
Rotational temperatures (K)	0.00614
	0.00590
	0.00337
Rotational constants (GHZ)	
X	0.12793
Y	0.12290
Z	0.07021
Total Energy Etotal(Kcal/mol)	259.642

Translational	0.889
Rotational	0.889
Vibrational	257.865

3.2.8 Global Reactivity descriptors

A good approach to predict global reactivity trends is to compute reactivity descriptors such as electronegativity (χ)= $-1/2(\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}}+\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}})$, chemical potential (μ)= $1/2(\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}}+\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}})$, global hardness (η)= $1/2(\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}}-\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}})$, global softness (S)= $1/2\eta$, $\Delta N_{\text{max}}=-\mu/\eta$ and electrophilicity index (ω)= $\mu^2/2\eta$. In molecular systems, Koopman's theorem is fundamentally used to ascertain chemical reactivity and site selectivity [37]. The above reactivity descriptors have been calculated and listed in Table 7.

ϵ_{H}	ϵ_{L}	$\epsilon_{\text{H}}-\epsilon_{\text{L}}$	I	A	χ	η	μ	ω	S	ΔN_{Max}
-8.8351	-2.4473	-6.3878	8.8351	8.8351	5.6412	-3.1938	-5.6412	-1.7662	0.1565	-17662

3.2.9 AIM approach

AIM approach shows the molecular graph of compound at B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level is presented in Fig 8. The strong, medium, weak H-bonds and their covalent, partially covalent and electrostatic nature can be denoted by $\nabla^2\rho(\text{BCP}) < 0$ and $H\text{BCP} < 0$, $\nabla^2\rho(\text{BCP}) > 0$ and $H\text{BCP} < 0$ and $\nabla^2\rho(\text{BCP}) > 0$ and $H\text{BCP} > 0$ respectively [48]. $\rho(\text{BCP})$ and $H\text{BCP}$ are Laplacian of electron

density and total electron density at bond critical point respectively. Parameters (geometrical and topological) for bonds of interacting atoms are given in Table 8. As all the $\nabla^2(\text{BCP})$ and $H\text{BCP}$ parameters were greater than zero hence C24—H44...O29 is weak interactions. The ellipticity (ϵ) at BCP is a sensitive index to monitor the n character of bond. The lower values of ellipticity confirm that there is delocalization of electron in aromatic ring [38].

Fig. 8 Molecular graph of the compound using AIM program at B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level ring critical points (small blue sphere), bond paths (red lines).

Table 8. Topological parameters for intramolecular interaction in compound; electron density (ρ_{BCP}), Laplacian of electron density ($\nabla^2\rho_{BCP}$), electron kinetic energy density (G_{BCP}), electron potential energy density (V_{BCP}), total electron energy density (H_{BCP}), Hydrogen bond energy (E_{HB}) at bond critical point (BCP).

Interactions	ρ_{BCP}	$\nabla^2\rho_{BCP}$	G_{BCP}	V_{BCP}	H_{BCP}	E_{HB}
C24—H44...O29	0.011215	0.046184	0.009690	-0.007833	0.057023	0.060444
ρ_{BCP} , $\nabla^2\rho_{BCP}$, G_{BCP} , V_{BCP} , H_{BCP} in a.u. and E_{HB} in (kcal/mol)						

3.2.10 Drug likeness and in-silico ADME prediction analysis

ADME is significant for inspecting the pharmacodynamics of material that could be used as target agents in drug revelation and design efforts. Numerous factors are provided by this tool, including lipophilicity, drug-likeness guidelines, and medicinal chemistry techniques [39]. Further, ADME is a balance of discrete structural and molecular properties which tested to attain efficient results to aid in drug discovery and formulation. So, it is the most novel method recommended to identify compounds that are contemplated for use in drugs that must respect certain rules that are significant. In addition, it plays a very substantial role in the very early phase of drug discovery to diminish the failing rate of drug candidates in clinical trials. By using the pharmacokinetics and physicochemical properties of compounds, we can

predict pre- determine their drug-likeness and oral bioavailability, which would relate to their drug bioactivities. The synthesized molecule shows druglike properties without straying from either Lipinski's rule of five, Ghose or Veber's criteria, according to an analysis of these features (Table 9) [40]. Physicochemical properties are in the following: Firstly, a crucial factor in determining molecular lipophilicity is logP. In this study, logP value of the synthesized compound is 3.28, which is also within an acceptable range. Therefore, the current molecule endorsed strong permeability and absorption across the cell membrane with a lipophilicity "log P" (octanol-water partition coefficient) character 5.0 [41]. Secondly, molecule have molecular weights that are more than 160 g/mol and less than 500 g/mol, which makes it simpler for these substances to be absorbed than substances with high molecular weights. Thirdly, the current compounds having H-bond donors (HBDs)

and H-bond acceptors (HBAs) less than 1 and 5, respectively. Fourth, a usually studied component identical with H- bonding (O and N atom counts) is total polar surface area (TPSA). All existing compounds have TPSA values that are lower than 140 Å². Fifth, the bioactivity score of compounds occurs at 0.55 and, which is a critical criterion for drug-likeness property. Finally, molar refraction value of the synthesized compounds is 117.37, which is within an acceptable range (Fig. 9). Therefore, the current compound has effective drug delivery properties and may be preferred for oral administration. Since all compounds comply with the Lipinski (often known as the “rule of five”), Ghose and Veber rules, they should

theoretically not pose oral bioavailability problems. According to pharmacokinetics properties from ADME results: Some of the present compounds have good responses for blood brain barrier (BBB) criteria, indicating that medications can cross the BBB. Consequently, these substances might be appropriate for the central nervous system. Additionally, the gastrointestinal absorption (GI) of all compounds was high except 8 and 9. The ability of a molecule to dissolve in both aqueous and non-aqueous media is crucial for the drug development process. Finally, skin permeability was measured by log K_p i.e. -6.09. The aforementioned data revealed that these compounds have a favorable ADME profile and drug resemblance.

Table 9. Estimations of ADMET and physicochemical properties of compound	
Physicochemical properties	ADME Data
MW	407
Logp	3.28
HBA	5
HBD	1
Bioavailability Score	0.55
TPSA	78.85
nRotB	2
MR	117.37
Lipinski Violation	0
Ghose Violation	0
GI Absorption	High
BBB Permeant	No
logK _p (cm/s)	-6.09

Fig. 9 Bioavailability radar of compound 6, using Swiss ADME

3.2.11 Molecular docking measurements:

In Molecular docking, structure-based drug design that simulates molecular and forecasts the binding affinities between receptors and ligands has been performed [42]. The molecule 6 interpreted with molecular docking inspection with the help of AutoDock 4.2.6 version of software. From the protein data bank, two proteins from the gene regulation-inhibitor complex (BL21(DE3)) with the PDBIDs 7DKP was invented. The binding energy of compounds 6 and the selected proteins of the 7DKP cell line was calculated using the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) in the AutoDock 4.2.6 programme [43]. 7DKP is an essential transcriptional and epigenetic regulator that influences the growth of microbes. According to molecular docking analyses, 6 reacted with several amino acids electrostatically, via Vander Waal interactions, and via hydrogen bonds. Two hydrogen bonds were formed with different amino acid residues at binding region of Asn33(b). The oxygen atom of pyridopyrimidine formed two hydrogen bonds with amino acid residue His8(B) and Asn33(B) at 3.32 Å and 3.37 Å respectively. The compound 6 showed highest affinity with protein of gene regulation-inhibitor complex (7DKP) (Fig. 13) with the total binding energy of -8.12 kcal/mol (Table 8). Hydrogen bonds and

hydrophobic interactions presents between different amino acid residues of protein are shown in Fig. 14. Compound 6 formed ten hydrophobic interactions with the selected protein as Gln47(B), Tyr11(B), Val48(B), Cys9(B), Pro10(B), Phe105(B), Tyr6(B), Tyr121(B), Lys125(B), Lys126(B) (Table 10). The best docked conformations are dogged by scaling the RMSD (Root Mean Square Deviation) between the predicted AutoDock4 conformation and the real framework with low binding energy conformations and using the clustering histogram with various RMSD values. Therefore, as compared to the conventional medication (bevacizumab), 6 demonstrated high potential binding energy against certain proteins. The examination of particular amino acid residues and their interactions with researched compounds supports the hypothesis that 6 might be employed as a medication in the future following completion of other crucial investigations (Fig. 10, 11). This is due to the fact that while approved medications are still necessary for the more specialized proteins of the gene regulation-inhibitor complex, the binding affinities towards the chemical are comparable. This provides more proof that the investigated compounds alter the normal shape of protein and alter the active site when they bind to the suggested sites.

Table 10. The summary of binding affinities (kcal/mol) and the H-bond as hydrophobic interactions in compound

Receptor Name	Residues involve in hydrogen bonding interaction	Residues involve in hydrophobic bonding interaction	No of bonds		Binding energy ΔG (Kcal/Mol)
			Hydrogen bond	Hydrophobic bond	
6	Asn33(B) O ₂ ...ND ₂ His8(B) O ₂ ...NE ₂	Gln47(B),	2	10	-8.12
		Tyr11(B)			
		Val48(B)			
		Cys9(B)			
		Pro10(B)			
		Phe105(B)			
		Tyr6(B)			
		Tyr121(B)			
		Lys125(B)			

		Lys126(B)		
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Fig. 10. The best docked conformation of compound with 7DKP of *Escherichia coli* representing different interactions.

Fig. 11. Histograms of the title molecule with 7DKP protein.

CONCLUSION

The studies gives a detailed account of synthesis and characterization of -(4-nitrophenyl) benzo [6,7] chromeno[3,2-e] pyrido[1,2-a] pyrimidin-

6(7H)-one using different characterization techniques (UV–Visible, FT-IR, ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and Mass). Computational studies was conducted and all the experimental and theoretically investigated values were found in good agreement with each other. Chemical shift values were in good agreement with experimental data as provided by GIAO NMR method. Ellipticity and intramolecular hydrogen bond interactions, as investigated by the AIM approach, depicted π -character of bonds in the aromatic ring and weak hydrogen bonds. Molecular docking analysis was performed with the active sites of targeted proteins, 7DKP to predict the binding mechanism of compound. The result showed good binding energy (-8.12 kcal/mol) with the protein of interest. The predicted ADME parameters reveal its drug-likeness properties and exhibited good oral bioavailability. The conclusion shows good evidence that the title compound serves as a potent antimicrobial agent.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

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